

PREDATION ATTEMPTS ON *RHYNCHOCYCLUS OLIVACEUS* (BIRDS: *RHYNCHOCYCLIDAE*) NESTS BY *PLECTUROCEBUS TOPPINI* THOMAS 1914 (PRIMATES: *PITHECIIDAE*), IN SOUTHWESTERN AMAZON

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Abstract

During a field work study of a group of Toppin's titi monkey (*Plecturocebus toppini*) in a forest fragment within urban area, we recorded four events of predation attempt on Eye-ringed flatbill (*Rhynchocyclus olivaceus*) nests by the monkeys. Although we did not recorded any successful attempt, these records may be evidence of an opportunistic behavior, reinforcing the hypothesis of the adaptive plasticity of this species on disturbed environments. *R. olivaceus* constructs its nest in the studied fragment at heights ranging from one to nine meters, most frequently in the class of two to four meters. The attempts were clearly intentional and are the first record of predation attempt on *Rhynchocyclus olivaceus* nests so far.

Key words: Forage, Fragmentation, Behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

Predation on nests is one of the main causes of reproductive failure of bird species [1]. Hence, careful selection of habitat for nest building is a critical decision that may diminish risk of predation. Birds possess adaptive adjustments in birth habitats or decisions regarding selection of nest sites, as well as dispersion strategies to avoid nest predation [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. In the case of neotropical birds, their nests are susceptible to a diverse variety of potential predators as birds of prey, snakes, insects, and mammals, which difficult the identification of the predator [6].

In order to reduce detectability and accessibility of predators, birds select types of habitat with specificities as sites with high vegetation cover, dense vegetation, and microhabitats [3]. Moreover, nest shape also may has direct relation with predation rate, for example, nests built in cavities (inside chambers in dead or alive tree trunks) have higher success rates than nests built

in open areas (hemispherical nests made from woven branches), because they are less detectable by predators [7, 6].

The order Passeriformes harbors the most diversified groups of birds (about 18% of the species of South America) [8, 9]. The Bird genus *Rhynchocyclus* is included in this order, and possess four species: *R. brevirostris*, *R. pacificus*, *R. fulvipectus*, and *R. olivaceus*. The last one is the only species of this genus that occurs in Brazilian territory [10]. Popularly known as Big-billed Beak, it is a passerine bird of the family Rhynchocyclidae. On the other hand, Titi monkeys comprise the most diverse group of species of neotropical primates, with 34 currently recognized taxa [11] and other species being recently described [12]. They inhabit primary, secondary forests, low strata of gallery forests or large clearings within the forest [13]. They can use from small fragments with five ha to larger areas, with up to 48 ha [14, 15, 16, 17]. They are highly frugivorous primates [18, 19] but complement their diet with leaves, flowers or insects. Bicca-Marques and Heymann (2013) compared eight species and presented values of fruit consumption that varied from 36 to 86% of the diet [20].

There are several studies related to the predation of nests by neotropical primates, as *Alouatta* spp. [21, 22], *Callicebus coimbrai* [23], *Cebus* sp. [24, 25, 26], *Callithrix* spp. [23], *Saimiri* sp. [25]. However, to date there are no records for the genus *Plecturocebus*. Thus, this study presents the first record of predation attempts on *Rhynchocyclus olivaceus* nests by *Plecturocebus toppini* during a study on food ecology and behavior of this primate in an urban forest fragment in the southwest of the Amazon.

2. METHODS

The records of attempted predation occurred at the Zoobotanical Park (PZ) (Figure 1), an area belonging to the Federal University of Acre (UFAC) in Rio Branco, Acre, Brazil (09°57'26"S, 067°52'25"W). PZ present an average altitude of 152.5 meters, forming an urban forest fragment with approximately 165 ha. The driest month in Rio Branco is June and the rainiest is February, with mean rainfall of 219 mm in the dry season and 1739 mm in the rainy season [27].

The vegetation of PZ is characterized by different successional stages, caused by the simultaneous mortalities of the bamboo species *Guadua weberbaueri*, which occurs every 32 years [28]. In general, the dynamics of bamboo growth and mortality generated three basic types of plant formations in the PZ: open tropical forest with palm trees, open palm forest with dominated bamboo and open bamboo forest with dominant bamboo [29].

A group of four individuals of *Plecturocebus toppini* was habituated and had their behavior and food ecology studies from February to December 2016, with monthly samplings of ten complete days (only on February we performed five full days). The behaviors were recorded using the scan sampling, with intervals of 15-minute, and *ad libitum* method [30]. The subjects observed were an adult male, an adult female, a subadult male (SM) and a subadult female (SF). For the identification of the nest and the species of bird, the study counted on the participation of professionals from the ornithology laboratory of the UFAC. The identification of the nests was carried out by Drielle Delgado Floriano (UFAC - Ornithology Laboratory)

Figure 1. Location of the Zoobotanical Park (PZ), belonging to the Federal University of Acre (UFAC), in the city of Rio Branco State of Acre Brazil.

3. RESULTS

During the study, four predation attempts were observed in different months, with duration varying between 11 - 22 seconds of foraging (Table 1). At each event, when the nest was reached, individuals stayed upside-down and placed the entire arm inside the nest, performing search movements (Figure 2). Among the individuals of the group, the adult female (AF) foraged in three different nests, while the adult male (AM) searched only one. Nevertheless, predation of eggs, puppies or any type of arthropod were observed.

The nest of *R. olivaceus* is pyriform [31, 32] closed type/retort/suspension structure, composed of the oologic chamber body and an access tunnel (external), built mainly with leaves, branches, bamboo leaves and fibers [33]. The support of the branch for nest construction is slightly smaller than 1 cm in diameter [34].

R. olivaceus constructs its nest in the studied fragment at heights ranging from one to nine meters, most frequently in the class of two to four meters. It is, therefore, a species that nest preferably in the low and medium understory of the forest [35].

4. DISCUSSION

A factor that directly influences the rate of predation is habitat quality, fragmented or degraded environments are subject to a higher predation rate [36, 37]. Predation in nests can cause declines in bird populations in forest fragments [38]). Interactions such as competition and predation may play an important role in bird communities in these environments [39].

Birds select nesting sites based on characteristics that provide greater security against predators [40]. At the time of nesting, the goal is to create adequate conditions for posture and incubation, providing shelter to nestlings (nestlings still in the nest) during their growth and to adults while they provide care for young children [41]. *R. olivaceus* has a preference for nest building on thin-walled branches, where surrounding vegetation does not touch the nest, which may also be related to anti-predation strategies [42].

The search for eggs in nests may be one of the methods that primates are using to obtain animal protein, and this type of behavior is considered opportunistic [22] as they attack any prey they encounter.

Lyra-Neves et al. (2007) [43] found that *Callithrix*

jacchus was responsible for the nest predation of eleven species of birds that lost their eggs and pups due to the attack of marmosets, even when birds exhibited defensive behavior. In *Alouatta guariba clamitans*, Bicca-Marques et al. (2014) have suggested that faunivory is an opportunistic and infrequent but intentional eating behavior [22]. Eggs (and pups) may be exploited under specific ecological circumstances, for example when there is little supply of protein-rich leaves in particular habitats.

Habitat reduction and loss in tropical forests damage ecosystems and communities, as fragmented forests change the population dynamics of fauna and vegetation, and especially affect food sources [44, 45]. *P. toppini* has a certain ecological plasticity in the exploitation of resources, which allows them to survive under the difficult circumstances of forest fragmentation [46].

Predation rate is frequently subtracted from landscape or habitat modification [47], fragmentation along with edge effect [48] can make these events more common. On the one hand the vegetation structure facilitates the visualization of nests and, on the other hand, lacking food resources, foraging in nests can be favored by predation of eggs, to acquire protein or arthropod resources in abandoned nests.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The only record of nest predation by Titi monkeys was observed in *Callicebus coimbrai* [23] in a forest fragment of more than 500 ha in the Atlantic forest. The event was considered rare and opportunistic. In PZ, although no predation record was observed in the nests, according to Floriano 2016 (unpublished), the species has a high nesting density at the study site [35]. All predation events recorded here are brief, lasting only a few seconds and also the duration of the study with the primates, we can infer that *P. toppini* is a potential predator in nests of this species of bird, occurring predations of eggs by the primates.

6. REFERENCES

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Table 1. Predation records attempted at the Zoobotanical Park in the year 2016.

Day/month	Season	Hour	Duration (seconds)	Height (meters)	Coordinates
19/02	Rainy	09:27	11	3,0	09°57.32'2"S; 67°52.39'1"W
18/08	Dry	11:35	17	1,8	09°57.32'7"S; 67°52.35'3"W
03/09	Dry	12:06	12	2,2	09°57.32'2"S; 67°52.33'4"W
08/10	Dry	11:46	22	2,0	09° 57.31'0"S; 67°52.37'8"W

Figure 2. Predation attempts on *Rhynchocyclus olivaceus* nests by *Plecturocebus toppini*. a) Individual of *P. toppini* foraging in the nest, b) Nest of the species *R. olivaceus*. Photo: Salatiel Clemente.